

Auxiliary Joining element with integrated Pin structures for mechanical joining of fiber-reinforced plastic/metal combinations

Per Heyser, M.Sc.* and Prof. Dr.-Ing. Gerson Meschut, Laboratory for Materials and Joining Technology (LWF®), Paderborn University, Germany
 Marcel Droß, M.Sc. and Prof. Dr.-Ing. Klaus Dröder, Institute of Machine Tools and Production Technology (IWF), TU Braunschweig, Germany

Motivation and objective

Initial situation

- High lightweight potential of fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP)
- Increasing use of FRP in industry
 - Multi material design with FRP and metal

State of the art

- FRP-components not suitable for punctual load → Lack of plasticity of the FRP, stress concentrations → Failure of the laminate/joint
- Current actions to increase strength: Increase in joints or laminate thickness → Increase in component weight ↔ Opposition to lightweight targets
 - Current FRP-metal joints only designed for low load capacity

Objective

- Development of an Auxiliary Joining element with integrated Pin structure (AJP) to increase the load-bearing capacity of mechanically joined FRP-metal joints
- Design of the pin structure for the optimization of the load condition in the FRP component

Mechanism of action of the structured Auxiliary Joining element

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Test materials and specimen geometries

- Materials used: GF-PA6 and HC340LA
- AJP material: X5CrNi18-10 (1.4301)
- AJP insertion: Using a WEBER Ultrasonics Weld & Cut SAPHIR-D2040 ultrasonic system

Modified shear tensile specimen with asymmetric flange

Material	Thickness (mm)	UTS (MPa)	Elongation (%)	Bearing strength (MPa)
GF-PA6	2.0	367 (0°) / 97 (45°) / 435 (90°)	2.3 (0°) / 29.7 (45°) / 2.6 (90°)	216
HC340LA	1.5	454	25.4	-

Mechanical properties of investigated materials according to DIN EN 2597, SEP1240 and DIN 50125

Results and discussion: Quasistatic shear test

Test method	Quasistatic shear test
Test velocity	v = 10 mm/min
Test machine	Zwick Z100
Steel material	HC340LA (t = 1.5 mm)
FRP material	GF-PA6 (t = 2.0 mm)
Joining technology / joining element	Screw: M5 x 20 (torque: 2 Nm)
Structured Auxiliary Joining element	1.4301 (t = 1.5 mm; Pin-length l = 1.3 mm)
Application method / number of specimen n	Ultrasonic (n = 5)
Specimen geometry	According to DVS/EFB 3480-1 Steel: 105 x 45 mm ² (edge distance: 8 mm) FRP: 110 x 45 mm ² (edge distance: 16 mm)

Conclusions

Results

- Development of different insertion methods: Ultrasonic-assisted insertion shows the highest usage potential
- Low-damage insertion with realistic station times possible
- Implementation of a manufacturing concept for Auxiliary Joining elements suitable for series production
- Design of a setting tool concept for blind riveting with Auxiliary Joining elements
- Corrosion protection of the Auxiliary Joining element by using titanium elements
- Reduced load on the FKV hole area by introducing the operating loads into the laminate via the pin structures of the Auxiliary Joining element

- Increase of the load bearing capacity more than 40%

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*Corresponding author: Per Heyser, Laboratory for Material and Joining Technology (LWF®), Paderborn University, Germany, per.heyser@lwf.uni-paderborn.de

Setting tool concept for blind riveting

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